

FLEXURAL FAILURE BEHAVIOR OF PITCH/PAN HYBRID UNIDIRECTIONAL CFRP

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ABSTRACT

This paper is concerned with the theoretical and experimental studies of the hybrid effect on the flexural behavior of pitch/PAN hybrid CFRP laminates consisting of various ratios of pitch-based and PAN-based unidirectional CFRP layers (XN40/25CH and T300/25CL layers). As a result, both slopes of the stress-strain curves of XN40/25CH and T300/25CL laminates become steeper as the tensile strain increases. The slopes decrease gradually as the compressive strain increases, and the compressive stresses approach a constant value. Therefore these CFRP's stress-strain curves indicate non-linear behavior. The constant value of compressive stress for XN40/25CH laminate is nearly a half of that of T300/25CL laminate. The hybrid CFRP laminates with T300/25CL layers on the compression side of XN40/25CH layers show a small decrease in flexural modulus and a large increase in the flexural strength compared with that of XN40/25CH laminate. This is the hybrid effect on the flexural behavior of hybrid CFRP laminates.

INTRODUCTION

The hybridization of composite materials has attracted much attention in the area of material design. Much research on the flexural behavior of carbon/aramid and carbon/glass fiber hybrid composite materials has been already reported [1-6]. However, there is limited results reported on flexural behavior of pitch-based/PAN-based carbon fiber hybrid composites.

This paper is concerned with the theoretical and experimental studies on the hybrid effect of the flexural behavior of pitch/PAN hybrid CFRP laminates consisting of various ratios of pitch-based and PAN-based unidirectional CFRP layers. The stress-strain curves of pitch-based unidirectional CFRP laminates (XN40/25CH laminates) and PAN-based unidirectional CFRP laminates (T300/25CL laminates) were measured over a wide range in

tension and compression. The flexural strength as well as the flexural modulus of hybrid CFRP laminates consisting of XN40/25CH and T300/25CL layers were numerically obtained based on laminated beam theory using the stress-strain relationship of XN40/25CH and T300/25CL laminates. These results are compared with the experimental results measured by 3-point bending tests for these hybrid CFRP laminates.

STRESS-STRAIN CURVES OF PITCH-BASED AND PAN-BASED UNIDIRECTIONAL CFRP LAMINATES

Unidirectional CFRP laminates using two types of fibers, a pitch-based and a PAN-based carbon fiber and two types of thermosetting resins were prepared. The pitch-based carbon fiber was XN40 (Nippon Oil). The PAN-based carbon fiber was T300 (Toray). The matrix resins are general purpose epoxy resins, 25CH and 25CL (Nippon Oil). The mechanical properties of these matrix resins are almost same. The glass transition temperature of these resins is 143 °C. The two kinds of prepreg sheets made from these resins and fibers were prepared for molding unidirectional CFRP laminates. These CFRP laminates were cured at 120 °C for 1 hrs and then cured for 2 hrs at 130 °C, and then 160 °C for 2 hrs. The fiber volume fraction of these CFRP laminates was approximately 60%.

Tensile stress-strain curves of pitch-based and PAN-based unidirectional CFRP laminates (XN40/25CH and T300/25CL laminates) were measured by tension test. Compressive stress-strain curves of those were indirectly obtained by moment-curvature curves from 4-point bending test. These curves are shown in Fig. 1. Both slopes of the stress-strain curves of XN40/25CH and T300/25CL laminates become steeper as tensile strain increases. The strengths of XN40/25CH and T300/25CL laminates are nearly identical. The slopes decrease gradually as compressive strain increases, and the compressive stresses approach a constant

Figure 1. Stress-strain curves of XN40/25CH and T300/25CL laminates.

values. Therefore these CFRP's stress- strain curves indicate non-linear behavior. The constant value of compressive stress for XN40/25CH laminate is nearly a half of that of T300/25CL laminate.

EXPLANATION OF HYBRID EFFECT WITH STRESS DISTRIBUTION MODEL

Flexural stress distribution model of XN40/25CH laminate and a hybrid CFRP laminate with T300/25CL layers on the compression side of XN40/25CH layers shown in Fig. 2 can be easily obtained from Fig. 1. It is predicted that the remarkable non-linear behavior on the load-deflection curve and the movement of neutral axis from center line occur for XN40/25CH laminate, and that these flexural behavior for hybrid CFRP laminate is restrained by the existence of T300/25CL layers on the compression side. Therefore, it is expected that the flexural strength of hybrid CFRP laminate become higher than that of XN40/25CH laminate by the increase of flexural stiffness in hybrid CFRP laminate.

Figure 2. Stress distribution model of XN40/25CH laminate and hybrid CFRP laminate.

LOAD-DEFLECTION CURVES OF HYBRID CFRP LAMINATES

The flexural strength as well as the flexural modulus for hybrid CFRP laminates consisting of XN40/25CH and T300/25CL layers were numerically obtained by laminated beam theory using the stress-strain relationship of XN40/25CH and T300/25CL laminates. The stress distribution in hybrid CFRP laminate shown in Fig. 2 can be obtained by the following equations using the stress-strain curves of XN40/25CH and T300/25CL laminates in Fig. 1. The distance from the neutral axis to center line of the hybrid CFRP laminate is calculated from equation (1):

$$b \int_{-h/2-e+h_1}^{h/2-e} \sigma_{XN}(\epsilon) dy + b \int_{-h/2-e}^{-h/2-e+h_1} \sigma_T(\epsilon) dy = 0, \quad \epsilon = \kappa y \quad (1)$$

where b is the width of specimen, h is the thickness of specimen, h_1 is the thickness of T300/25CL layer, e is the distance from the neutral axis to center line, $\sigma_{XN}(\epsilon)$ and $\sigma_T(\epsilon)$ are the stress distributions of XN40/25CH and T300/25CL layers, respectively. κ is the curvature of beam. Moment of hybrid CFRP laminate is calculated by equation (2)

$$M = b \int_{-h/2-e+h_1}^{h/2-e} \sigma_{XN}(\epsilon) \cdot y dy + b \int_{-h/2-e}^{-h/2-e+h_1} \sigma_T(\epsilon) \cdot y dy \quad (2)$$

Load-deflection curves of the hybrid CFRP laminate can be easily obtained from the relationship between moment M and curvature κ .

EXPERIMENTAL STUDY ON HYBRID EFFECT

LAMINATE CONSTITUTION

Five kinds of unidirectional hybrid CFRP laminates with T300/25CL layer on the compression side of XN40/25CH layer were prepared. The laminate constitutions are shown in Fig 3.

Figure 3. Laminate constitutions of hybrid CFRP laminates.

3-POINT BENDING TEST

3-point bending test for hybrid CFRP laminates were conducted by using Instron type testing machine. The nominal dimensions of the test specimen are 120X15X3 mm (length, width, thickness). The span length is 100mm. The temperature is 30° C, and deflection rate is 5mm/min. The load was applied on the surface of T300/25CL layer for all hybrid CFRP laminates. Aluminum foil was inserted under the loading point to avoid the influence of stress concentration.

FLEXURAL FRACTURE MODE

Fractographs of XN40/25CH, T300/25CL and hybrid CFRP laminates are shown in Fig 4. The fracture of all CFRP laminates occurs in tensile mode at the surface layer on the tension side of specimens.

Figure 4. Fractographs of XN40/25CH, T300/25CL and hybrid CFRP laminates from 3-point bending test.

LOAD-DEFLECTION CURVES

Typical load-deflection curves of XN40/25CH, T300/25CL and hybrid CFRP laminates obtained from 3-point bending test are shown in Fig. 5. Thick line in this figure shows the theoretical load-deflection curves obtained from the stress-strain curves of XN40/25CH and T300/25CL laminates. The theoretical load-deflection curves agree well with experimental ones.

FLEXURAL STRENGTH AND MODULUS

The flexural strength and modulus of hybrid CFRP laminates for various laminate constitution are shown in Fig. 6. Thick and thin lines in this figure show the theoretical values and the hollow and solid symbols show the experimental values. The hybrid CFRP laminates with T300/25CL layer on the compression side of XN40/25CH layer showed a small decrease in flexural modulus and a large increase in the flexural strength compared with that of

XN40/25CH laminates. The experimental results agree well with theoretical results. Therefore, the hybrid effect on the flexural behavior of pitch/PAN hybrid CFRP laminates is confirmed and the mechanism of hybrid effect is clarified.

Figure 5. Load-deflection curves of XN40/25CH, T300/25CL and hybrid CFRP laminates.

Figure 6. Flexural strength and modulus versus laminate constitutions.

CONCLUSION

This paper is concerned with the theoretical and experimental studies of the hybrid effect on the flexural behavior of pitch/PAN hybrid CFRP laminates consisting of various constitution of pitch-based and PAN-based unidirectional CFRP layers (XN40/25CH and T300/25CL layers). As a result, both slopes of the stress-strain curves of XN40/25CH and T300/25CL laminates become steeper as the tensile strain increases. The slopes decrease gradually as the compressive strain increases, and each compressive stress approaches a constant value, respectively. Therefore these CFRP's stress-strain curves indicate non-linear behavior. The constant value of compressive stress for XN40/25CH laminates is nearly a half of that of T300/25CL laminates. The hybrid CFRP laminates with T300/25CL layer on the compression side of XN40/25CH layer show a small decrease in flexural modulus and a large increase in the flexural strength compared with that of XN40/25CH laminates. This is the hybrid effect on the flexural behavior of hybrid CFRP laminates.

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